

TEACHING READING THROUGH PHONETIC ACTIVITIES TO YOUNG
CHILDREN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7883840>

Azieva Tumaris

2nd year student of KKSU faculty of Foreign languages

Khadjieva Dilbar

Ph.d.dotc.of English Linguistics of KKSU

Abstract: *This article proposes the important role of learning reading fluently in English, teaching pronunciation of letters and reading, the differences in the writing and pronunciation of letters, the role of parents and teachers in the process of teaching reading to a child, useful methods and several characteristics that a teacher should have.*

Key words: *teaching reading, reading fluently, letters, sounds, beginners, phonetics, phonics, successful teacher, phonics, fluency,*

During the stages of language learning, a child may face various difficulties. One of them may be learning fluent reading in foreign language. The pronunciation and writing of words differ in some languages, and English is one of such language. In order to learn to read in foreign language, it is necessary to learn the main principles of phonetics by teachers and parents. They can give a help for children to read fluently. As pupils become better and better in READING the foreign language, the printed word becomes the main source of expanding and strengthening the language.

Reading is the language skill which is easiest to keep up [5,49]. Some children are quick to catch on. This increases their language skills, and at the same time other children have slower understanding process, for them we should give more attention on teaching because their first knowledge can influence to become a great person. The ability to read and understand a key role in learning by taking in a lot of information.

In this article, I'll try to discuss about the influents of adults on children's fluency reading, the differences of words in English between writing and reading, and the method which is used to teach reading to children.

Phonemes combine to form syllables and words. A few words have only one phoneme, Such as a or oh. Most words consists of a blend of phonemes, such as go with two phonemes or check with three phonemes, or stop with four phonemes. Phonemes are different from graphemes, which are units of written language and which represent phonemes in the spelling of words. Graphemes may consist of one letter for example P, T, K, A, N or multiple letters CH, SH, TH, CK, EA, IGH, each symbolize one phoneme [4:11]. By looking at these information we can imagine that phonemes are different from graphemes. The table of phonemes is given below

VOWELS	monophthongs				diphthongs		Phonemic Chart voiced unvoiced	
	i: sheep	ɪ ship	ʊ good	u: shoot	ɪə here	eɪ wait		
	e bed	ə teacher	ɜ: bird	ɔ: door	ʊə tourist	ɔɪ boy		əʊ show
	æ cat	ʌ up	ɑ: far	ɒ on	eə hair	aɪ my	aʊ cow	
CONSONANTS	p pea	b boat	t tea	d dog	tʃ cheese	dʒ June	k car	g go
	f fly	v video	θ think	ð this	s see	z zoo	ʃ shall	ʒ television
	m man	n now	ŋ sing	h hat	l love	r red	w wet	j yes

/1:33/

Children should also learn to identify letters and know that a pronounced word can be divided into a sequence of sounds corresponding to these letters. For example, to complain to child the phonemes of letters, we should show some samples of words in the text and read:

How many balls have you?

Have you a **cat**? Yes we have.

How many kittens has the cat? It has **one** kitten.

How **many ducks** have you? We have two ducks and ten **ducklings**.

How many hens have you? I **have** eight hens.

How many **cows** have you? I have one cow

How many **dogs** have **you**? I have **two** dogs

How many **books** has **this** boy? He has eleven.

How many **copy-books** has this **little** girl? She has **four**.

How many **pens** has she? She has ten pens.

How many **kittens** have you? I have **three** kittens. [6\30]

Letter Aa

Cat	kæt
Many	'meni
Have	hæv

Letter

Oo

How	hau
One	wʌn
Cow	kau
Dog	dɒg
You	ju:
Two	tu:
Book	buk
Copy-book	'kʌpi buk
Four	fɔ:

Letter

Ii

I	ai
Kitten	'kitn
Little	'litl
This	ðis

Letter

Uu

Duck	dʌk
Duckling	'dʌkliŋ

Letter

Ee

Pen	pen
Three	θri:

By learning sounds children can easily read, and understand the text. By the way phonetics helps to develop their speaking ability in foreign language. How teachers and schools can help parents support early literacy:

- * Teachers can point out that learning to identify words by demonstrating effective story book reading while parents are visiting or during a home visit.
- * Teachers can encourage parents to read some rhyming books to their and develop a family repertoire of favorite rhymes.

Teachers can help parents comprehend and appreciate what a child's sometimes unconventional spelling reveals about his or her knowledge of letter sound. Examples of how children's spontaneous spelling becomes more conventional over time may give parents needed reassurance. /3:17/

Reading with children, making favorite books make also good effect for their reading ability. They develop their knowledge, and they want to take more information, learn more things voluntarily. Teaching English to children is not an easy job. But it is also not difficult, if we already know how to do it. Many researchers do believe that a successful language teacher of children should possess some characteristics as follows :

- * Must be energetic and patient
- Must love children .
- * Must pay attention to individual differences.
- * Must encourage , encourage , and encourage
- * Must let children see the beautiful and useful aspects of the language.
- * Must let them love you as the language teacher and the new language as well
- * Must know the techniques of teaching
- * Must respect children as human
- * Must start teaching to children as soon as possible . [2,4]

Looking at these characters, we can say that while teaching English to children, the teacher should be mindful and kind to them, pay attention to each student, and respect. These characteristics will help student to see you as a favorite teacher and motivate child to learn more English.

We can use interesting methods, group games, tasks, individual tasks for teaching children a foreign language. . Furthermore beginners in

English reading have some difficulties in reading words and understand their meaning. It is important to remember that learning to read involves various different skills and these skills children need in order to successfully learn how to read.

For example: Phonemic awareness- the ability to hear and use skillfully the differ sounds in word.

Phonics – recognizing the sound of letters and their overall sound they make.
Vocabulary – understanding the meaning of the words and their connection.

Reading comprehension – understanding the overall meaning of the text.

Fluency – reading with speed by the way understand.

It is very important for child learn reading and ability to read fluently.

It may be a key of new knowledge in learning English.

The books in English may be very interesting for them and they may be into learning this language.

To teach a child to read the help of a teacher and also parents is big.

Because they know more than a child, and for child it may be exciting to learn something with them.

Furthermore in teaching reading process we should not forget about some methods and games which are useful for a kid.

Using methods truly can accelerate the process of learning reading.

Teaching English to kids is always fun.

REFERENCES:

1. Arif Savaş Geylanioglu “ Developing English Language learners pronunciation through conceptualization” 2016
2. Masoud Hashemi “Teaching English to children: A unique, challenging Experience for teachers, effective teaching ideas” 2011
3. Nancy Ewald, Cathy M. “ Reading with young children” Washington 1993
4. National Reading Panel, “Teaching children to read” reports of the subgroups. 2000
5. Wendy A Scott, Lisbeth H. Ytreberg “Teaching English to children” 1991
6. Валентина Скультэ “Английский язык для детей” Tashkent 2010